

marker #9A, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

0.005

marker #41

0.005

marker #44

0.004

marker #45_p1, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

marker #45_p2

0.003

marker #46

0.003

marker #50, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

0.002

marker #51_1, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

0.004

marker #52

0.005

marker #54_p1

0.003

marker #54_p2

0.001

marker #56

0.003

marker #57, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

0.005

marker #58, modified following Yang and Smith 2014

0.005

marker #63

0.004